

Supplementary Material S6.- Spatial structure of the residuals of GLM models accounting for species richness variations on studied islands with all the considered predictors (complete models). Background colours represent the results of a Trend Surface Analysis (TSA) on these residuals, and circles represent the values of these residuals for each island. The range of colours means the same residual values on the circles and on the TSA. Negative residuals represent overpredictions.

Scarabaeinae

Aphodiidae

Geotrupinae

